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Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury-(II) Complexes with a Tridentate ONO Donor Schiff Base

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In continuation of our earlier reports¹⁻³ on the study of fungitoxicity of complex compounds having mono- and bi-pyrazolones as ligands, the present paper deals with the synthesis of a Schiff base by reacting furfuraldehyde with 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-5-one and preparation and characterisation of its Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of Schiff base: Ethanolic solutions of 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-5-one and furfuraldehyde in 1 : 1 molar ratio were mixed and refluxed over a water-bath for 2 h. The resulting Schiff base that separated out on cooling the mixture was filtered, washed with ethanol, air-dried and analysed, m.p. 198°.

Preparation of complexes: The Schiff base dissolved in dioxane and the metal chlorides in ethanol were mixed in 1 : 1 ratio and refluxed at 120° for ~ 2 h. The complexes that separated out on keeping the solution overnight were filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried under reduced pressure and analysed.

Conductance of 10⁻³ M solutions in dimethyl formamide were measured using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic moments μ_{eff} were determined by Gouy method at room temperature (300 K). Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 221 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra of 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in DMF on a Hilger Watt Uvispek spectrophotometer. The results are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes have the composition [MLCl₂.H₂O], where, M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; L=Schiff base. The cobalt complex was pink, nickel complex greenish yellow, copper complex coffee-coloured, zinc complex white, cadmium complex yellow and mercury complex grey in colour.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
	Metal	N	
L	—	14.52 (14.94)	—
[CoLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	13.42 (13.74)	9.45 (9.79)	5.0
[NiLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	13.25 (13.69)	9.38 (9.79)	3.13
[CuLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	14.28 (14.65)	9.25 (9.68)	1.78
[ZnLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	14.85 (15.02)	9.32 (9.64)	—
[CdLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	22.86 (23.30)	9.29 (8.70)	—
[HgLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	34.50 (35.16)	7.02 (7.36)	—

*L=Schiff base derived from furfuraldehyde and 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-5-one (C₁₆H₁₆N₂O₂).

Low molar conductances indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. In the ligand, $\nu_{C=O}$ band appearing at 1 640 cm⁻¹ undergoes a bathochromic shift of ca 10–20 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes indicating the bonding of the Schiff base to the metal ion through carbonyl oxygen. The lowering of $\nu_{C=N}$ ligand band (1 595 cm⁻¹)⁴⁻⁶ to ca 1 580 cm⁻¹ in the complexes showed the azomethine nitrogen coordination to the metal ions. The ligand ν_{C-O} (furan ring) band⁷ (1 020 cm⁻¹) shifted to ca 940 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes, suggesting the involvement of furan oxygen atom to the metal atoms. The sharp far-ir band at ca 500 cm⁻¹ of the complexes was assigned to the metal–oxygen (furan) ring stretching vibration⁸⁻¹¹. The 1 460 and 1 420 cm⁻¹ bands appearing both in the ligand and the complexes were attributed to the bending vibration of the pyrazole skeleton¹². The presence of coordinated water molecule in all the metal complexes is shown¹³ by the appearance of bands at ca 3 300–3 450 cm⁻¹ followed by another peak at ca 840–860 cm⁻¹ assignable to the OH stretching and rocking vibrations, respectively.

The μ_{eff} values of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were found to be 5.0, 3.12 and 1.78 B.M., respectively, indicating an octahedral geometry around the metal ions¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

The uv-visible spectra of the ligand exhibited two bands at 273 (36 630) and 337 nm (29 673 cm⁻¹) assignable to $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions, respectively. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complex exhibited three spin-allowed transitions at 9 465, 15 100 and 25 540 cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The spectral parameter *B* has been calculated¹⁷ by utilising the equation, $B = (\nu_2 + \nu_3 - 3\nu_1)/15$. The

lower value of B (816 cm^{-1}) indicates considerable covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond¹⁸. The lowering of ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.59) from 1.8 shows high-spin octahedral configuration for the complex. The value of covalency parameter (β) was found to be 0.78.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complex exhibited bands at 8 700, 17 500 and 21 540 cm^{-1} attributable to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively. The ligand field parameters like B (818 cm^{-1}), $10 Dq$ ($9\ 020 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), ν_2/ν_1 (0.02), β_{8g} (0.84) and (19.04) along with higher μ_{eff} value (Table 1) suggest an octahedral stereochemistry.

The Co^{II} complex showed one broad band at (13 900–15 800 cm^{-1}) (185 cm^{-1}) which can be assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition which is a characteristic of distorted octahedral configuration¹⁹.

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Complexes of 4-Amino-3-mercapto-5-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,4-triazole with Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc- and Cadmium-(II) Ions

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IN the present paper we report the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,4-triazole (AMOPTH₂) with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} .

Experimental

AMOPTH₂ was prepared as reported¹.

Preparation of metal complexes: Aqueous ethanolic solutions of metal(II) halide (0.005 mol in 60 ml) and the ligand (0.01 mol in 100 ml) were mixed in hot. pH of the mixed solution was raised slowly to 7–8 by adding concentrated ammonia and refluxed for 0.5 h. The Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes separated immediately but the Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes separated on adding equal volume of water. The product was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried at 90–100° (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis %: Found (Calcd.)		μ_{eff}^* B.M.
		M	N	
$\text{Co}(\text{AMOPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	Brown	19.65 (19.58)	18.61 (18.60)	4.82
$\text{Ni}(\text{AMOPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	Bluish green	19.63 (19.52)	18.54 (18.62)	3.22
$\text{Cu}(\text{AMOPT})$	Brown	23.62 (23.57)	20.66 (20.77)	1.51
$\text{Zn}(\text{AMOPT})$	White	24.32 (24.09)	20.59 (20.63)	Diamag.
$\text{Cd}(\text{AMOPT})$	White	35.43 (35.30)	17.51 (17.58)	Diamag.

*At 304 K.

Ir, uv and visible reflectance spectra, and magnetic susceptibilities were determined as usual. For calculating effective magnetic moment values, correction was made for TIP contribution².

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analyses (Table 1) indicate that AMOPTH₂ forms 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) complexes with bivalent metal ions. The complexes, in general, are slightly soluble in organic solvents like methanol, ethanol and acetone but are insoluble in water. The methanol solutions of the com-